

EFFECT OF METALLIC SOAPS ON POLYMERISATION

BY JYOTIRINDRA NATH SEN AND SANTI R. PALIT

Effect of a few oil-soluble, surface-active agents and the oleates of Cr, Ag, Cd, Pb, Cu on the benzoyl peroxide catalysed polymerisation of styrene in solution and that of the soaps of Mn, Zn, Cd, Co, Ni, Al, Fe etc. on the polymerisation of methyl methacrylate and styrene in absence of peroxide catalyst have been studied. In the former case aerosol and Cu oleate retarded, and cetavlon inhibited polymerisation. Other soaps studied showed only a very slight retarding effect.

In the uncatalysed polymerisation of methyl methacrylate Mn oleate inhibited and Zn oleate and Cd oleate retarded polymerisation, all other soaps catalysed it. With styrene all soaps excepting that of manganese, which inhibited polymerisation, showed definite catalytic activity.

In continuation of our previous work (this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 385) we carried out a number of experiments with various metallic soaps and oil-soluble, surface-active agents on polymerisation as a preliminary survey of the whole field. As we now intend to limit ourselves to a closer study of only one or two systems from this survey, which seems to us of immediate interest with regard to the fundamentals of polymerisation kinetics, we record only the general results obtained.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The experimental method and technique were the same as previously reported (*loc.cit.*). Viscosity measurements were carried out in benzene solution at 35° with the help of two Ostwald type viscometers of flow time 180 and 230 sec. respectively. Intrinsic viscosity (η) was obtained by extrapolating η_{sp}/c vs. c to zero concentration ($\eta_{sp} = \eta_s/\eta_0 - 1$) = $t_s/t_0 - 1$, where η_s and η_0 are the viscosities and t_s and t_0 , the times of flow of the solution and the solvent respectively, and c is the concentration expressed in g./100 ml. solvent.

TABLE I

Polymerisation of 1.15 M styrene in benzene with 0.96% benzoyl peroxide and various additives at 80°.

Time=4 hours.

Additive.	Conc. of additive (g./100 c.c. soln).	Yield.	Remarks.	Additive.	Conc. of additive (g./100 c.c. soln).	Yield.	Remarks
None	Nil	20.17%					V. S effective
Chromium oleate	1.12	20.05	Not effective	Leda oleate	3.4	19.2%	Do
			„	Triton N-100	3.2	19.1	Do
Silver oleate	0.013	19.9	„	Aerosol O.S	2.0	17.6	Small retardation
Cadmium oleate	1.5	19.7	Very slight effective	Copper oleate	0.01	11.9	Retardation
Glycerine mono	1.3	19.6	„	Coper oleate	2.0	0.96	Strong retardation
sterate			„	Cetavlon	2.6	0.0	Inhibition

DISCUSSION

Polymerisation in presence of Catalyst.—The results of benzoyl peroxide catalysed polymerisation of styrene (1.15 M) in benzene at 80° with different additives are presented in Table I. The results show that for a period of polymerisation of 4 hours and a yield of 20.17% in the reaction where no additive has been added (control experiment), cetavlon totally inhibits polymerisation, and copper oleate (2 g. per 100 c.c. solution) produces only 1.0% yield for the same period of 4 hours *i. e.* it behaves as a strong retarder of polymerisation. Effectiveness of copper oleate as a retarder is found to diminish, as expected, with decrease in its concentration. Chromium oleate and silver oleate practically exert no influence on polymerisation; cadmium oleate, lead oleate, glycerol monostearate and triton N-100 have a very small retarding effect. Though small, the tendency to retard polymerisation by the above mentioned additives seems real and the lack of any pronounced retarding effect may partly be due to the presence of rather a high concentration of benzoyl peroxide catalyst which would mask the effects produced by the additives in such a dilute solution of the monomer. Aerosol O.S., however, retards polymerisation and produces a yield of 17.6% after 4 hours.

We, however, realised that in order to assess the true effect of these additives it would be better to work in systems without peroxide, and hence in all our later experiments we studied the effect of additives in uncatalysed polymerisation. The results are reported in the next section.

It is, however, remarkable that cetavlon is capable of completely inhibiting polymerisation against high peroxide concentration and high temperature. This contrasts strongly with the behaviour of the same substance in a reduction-activation aqueous system where even trace quantities have been found by Baxendale, Evans and Kilham (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1946, 42, 668) to strongly catalyse polymerisation. It is suggested that cetavlon or similar substances be used as commercial inhibitors offering the advantage of complete removal of the monomer by distillation.

Polymerisation in absence of Peroxide Catalyst: Styrene.—As only a few soaps are soluble in pure styrene, we have studied polymerisation of 4.6 molar solution of styrene in benzene, in which solvent soaps of magnesium, zinc, nickel, cobalt and manganese are freely soluble. The results of these experiments are shown in Table II and graphically represented in Fig. 1.

All the metallic soaps we have studied are found to catalyse the polymerisation of styrene though of course their catalytic power, as indicated by the initial slopes of the yield-time curves, vary for the different soaps. For, approximately, the same concentration of the soaps the relative effectiveness of the different metallic soaps as catalysts for styrene polymerisation follows the order: zinc oleate, magnesium oleate, cobalt oleates, nickel oleate, ferric stearate, ferric oleate.

It should be pointed out here that some of the soaps, like nickel and cobalt oleates, which were found to retard the polymerisation of 1.15% molar styrene in benzene in presence of 0.06% benzoyl peroxide (Sen, Sen Gupta and Palit, this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 385) actually catalysed polymerisation in this case, *i. e.*, in the absence of benzoyl peroxide.

TABLE II

Polymerisation of 6.48M styrene in benzene at 60.4° in presence of additives.

Additive	Conc. of additive (mole/mole monomer).	Time.	% Yield.		D.P.*
None	Nil	21.5 hrs.	2.11	3.85	17,420
		42.0	4.20		
		64.5	6.85		
		69.0	7.27		
Manganese oleate	2.497×10^{-4}	42.0	0.00	—	
Zinc oleate	2.517×10^{-4}	42.0	5.05	—	
		68.0	8.38		
Magnesium oleate	2.523×10^{-4}	42.0	5.32	3.19	13,450
		68.0	9.40		
Cobalt oleate	3.321×10^{-4}	42.0	6.38	2.94	11,980
		68.0	11.08		
Nickel oleate	2.505×10^{-4}	42.0	8.02	2.92	11,900
		68.0	14.40		
Ferric stearate	2.512×10^{-4}	21.5	6.36	2.82	11,330
		68.0	13.80		
Ferric oleate	2.350×10^{-4}	21.5	6.25	1.85	6,301
		42.0	12.00		
		64.5	15.62		
		95.0	17.7		

* Calculated from equation $K_m M^a$, $K_x = 1.2 \times 10^{-4}$, $a = 0.72$

(D'Alelio, "Experimental Plastics and Synthetic Resins", p. 71, John Wiley and Sons, Inc., 1946)

FIG. 1.

Temp. 60.4°; styrene (6.48 mol./litre)

The retardation in the peroxide-catalysed polymerisation is possibly due to some wastage of peroxide by interaction with the metallic soaps or other complicating factors. Manganese oleate inhibits polymerisation totally. The behaviour of ferric oleate and ferric stearate as a good catalyst is maintained here. From the curves it appears that at the initial stage the rates of polymerisation with the two ferric soaps are practically the same.

Polymerisation in absence of Peroxide Catalyst : Methyl Methacrylate: Comparative Yields.—Three series of polymerisation experiments were conducted with methyl methacrylate with the addition of a small proportion (2.4 mols. per 10,000 mols. monomer) of an added metallic soap and the extent of polymerisation was measured after a convenient interval for each series. Two of these were methyl methacrylate in bulk, one at 35° and the other at 80°. As most of the metallic soaps were found to dissolve in the monomer only with great difficulty or not at all, another series of experiments was run at 35° with the monomer diluted with an equal volume of benzene to impart solubility to a large number of soaps, thus making their examination possible. The results are graphically represented in Fig. 2.

Referring to Fig. 2A it will be observed that at as low a concentration as 2.4 mols. metallic soaps per 10,000 mols. of monomer, cobalt and iron strongly accelerate polymerisation, whereas copper and manganese practically stop the reaction. By the time the thermal reaction (control) gives a yield of only 5%, iron oleate produces a yield of over 21% and the acceleration by cobalt oleate is so strong that the whole tube sets to a solid mass much earlier than the time allowed for the reaction. The polymer obtained with cobalt was found to swell but not to dissolve in benzene even on keeping in contact with the solvent for several days, and hence, the exact value of the yield of the polymer could not be ascertained. It is rather strange that this catalyst can produce a polymer which is insoluble in such a good solvent, a behaviour which is not known to occur with peroxide catalysts. It will be observed that iron oleate is a somewhat less powerful catalyst than iron laurate. This is further corroborated by our data at the same temperature in benzene solution, where the difference is less marked (Fig. 2, c). However, at 80° this difference seems to vanish.

The least understood feature of these data, however, is the effect of dilution on the catalysed reaction. When the monomer is diluted with an equal volume of benzene, the yield, calculated on the assumption of a linear yield curve, falls by about four times from 1.42 yield % per day to 0.33, whereas with ferric oleate as catalyst, dilution has a smaller effect on the yield % per day (5.35 to 2.13) and with ferric laurate the yield % per day is still less affected (2.56 to 1.69).

On repeating the same experiments in bulk at 80° with a conversion of about 4 times in the control experiment, we have observed very unexpectedly that the picture is completely changed (Fig. 2, B). In this case, we find cobalt and iron oleate to have fairly strong catalytic effects. In fact, the catalytic effect of iron oleate is very strong, almost as strong as that of cobalt oleate in the previous case. Cobalt oleate in this case also has a very strong catalytic effect producing a yield of about double the amount produced in the control reaction. As usual, manganese oleate gave no yield, thus behaving as an inhibitor.

FIG 2

Conc. of catalyst in all runs is 2.42×10^{-4} mols./litre.

- A—Temp. 35° ; methylmethacrylate (bulk) (Co oleate sets to a hard insoluble polymer),
 B—Temp. 80° ; Do
 C—Temp 35° ; Do (1 : 1 by vol, in benzene)
 (Fe oleate and laurate set into a hard insoluble polymer).

Copper in any form is known to have a strong retarding or inhibitory effect, and we have verified the same in our previous work with styrene (*loc. cit.*). In the present study with uncatalysed methyl methacrylate polymerisation, diluted with an equal volume of benzene we unexpectedly observe copper oleate to have a small catalytic effect. We have confirmed by repeated experiments that this capricious behaviour of copper is a real one and is not due to any experimental uncertainty. Indeed, the results presented herein show that the retarding effect of copper is decreased giving place of acceleration by dilution of the monomer or by a rise of temperature.

Referring to Fig. 2,c for 1:1 monomer-benzene mixture, it may be observed that at 35° , out of the seven soaps studied iron, copper, aluminium and nickel act as catalysts, whereas cadmium and zinc act as retarders, and manganese as an inhibitor. The behaviour of iron and manganese is somewhat similar to their action on bulk polymerisation at the same temperature (Fig. 2,A). Of the new soaps studied that of aluminium behaves as a strong catalyst. This powerful catalytic effect of aluminium soap perhaps undisputedly proves that the catalytic behaviour of the metallic soaps has nothing to do with variable valency of the metal.

Complete Yield-time Curve.—A rough survey of the field being obtained in the above experiments, it was decided to determine a full yield-time curve for all the metallic soaps to have a fair idea of their relative efficiency. This has been done and the results are presented in Fig. 3. These experiments were performed at 80° with methyl methacrylate, diluted with an equal volume of benzene. The results in the main corroborate our foregoing findings with single tube experiments. It is further seen that no spurious effect due to impurities are involved, as otherwise it would not have been possible to obtain such consistent data throughout such a long period, producing a high conversion. It is observed that manganese behaves as an inhibitor, and that zinc and cadmium are retar-

FIG. 3.

ders, whereas aluminium, nickel, iron, copper and cobalt are all strong catalysts for polymerisation under the experimental conditions. Cobalt, as previously observed, has got the strongest effect producing nearly 4 times more yield of the polymer than in the control experiment. Next to cobalt comes iron oleate and laurate, whose curves are practically the same. Aluminium and nickel come next. The effect of zinc and cadmium seem to be those of pure retarding effects without showing any period of inhibition, whereas manganese definitely shows a rather long period of inhibition. The inhibition of manganese is very unexpected as both cobalt and manganese soaps are known to be powerful accelerators for polymerisation of drying oils, and it is difficult to see by what mechanism this inhibition is produced.

The effect of temperature and dilution is worth noting. If we suppose that the thermal polymerisation, and that initiated by metallic soaps are quite independent of each other, and if we assume for rough calculation that the yield is roughly proportional to time, we can easily observe from Fig. 2c and Fig. 3 that a rise of temperature of 45° (from 35° to 80°) increases the speed of the iron laurate or oleate catalysed reaction barely 20 times or less. In other words, polymerisation initiated by metal soaps is less sensitive to temperature than thermal polymerisation. We have already pointed out a diminished sensitivity of the speed of the former reaction to dilution with benzene as compared to the purely thermal polymerisation. Of course, the above conclusions are based on the concept that the thermal and the catalysed polymerisation are concurrent independent reactions which, however, is yet to be proved.

Measurement of molecular weight or degree of polymerisation of the products obtained in catalysed and control experiments have not been made in a systematic manner. Nevertheless, the values of intrinsic viscosity and degree of polymerisation, calculated therefrom, as given in Table II, show that the D. P. of samples produced in the control experiment is much higher than those of samples produced in the metallic soap catalysed reaction (Sen and Palit, *Nature*, 1950, **166**, 603). Though this is quite in conformity with our expectations, it must be pointed out at the same time that the D.P. is never so low (*ca.* 1000) as to justify the assumptions of polar polymerisation (Heiligmann, *J. Polymer Sci.*, 1944, **66**, 1594).

INDIAN ASSOCIATION OF
THE CULTIVATION OF SCIENCE,
CALCUTTA.

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